

DEVELOPMENT OF FOKKINK-FOKKINK-WANG'S GENERATING FUNCTION FOR $FFW(n)$

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Abstract:

In 1995, R. Fokkink, W. Fokkink and Wang defined the $FFW(n)$ in terms of $s(\pi)$, where $s(\pi)$ is the smallest part of partition π . In 2008, Andrews obtained the generating function for $FFW(n)$. In 2013, Andrews, Garvan and Liang extended the FFW -function and obtained the similar expressions for the spt -function and then defined the spt -crank generating functions. They also defined the generating function for $FFW(z, n)$ in various ways. This paper shows how to find the number of partitions of n into distinct parts with certain conditions and shows how to prove the Theorem 1 by induction method. This paper shows how to prove the Theorem 2 with the help of two generating functions.

Keywords:

Distinct parts, FFW -function, positive divisors, smallest part, spt -function, spt -crank.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we give some related definitions of $P(n)$, $FFW(n)$, $d(n)$, $(x)_\infty$, $(x^2; x)_\infty$, $(zx)_\infty$, $(x)_k$ and $(x^{k+1}; x)_\infty$. We give two tables for $FFW(5)$ and $FFW(6)$ respectively and discuss the generating functions for $FFW(n)$ and then shows a relation related to the term $d(n)$. We discuss the various generating functions for $FFW(z, n)$ and prove the Corollary I for proving the fundamental Theorem 1 containing three parts and prove the Theorem 2

$$FFW(z, n) = \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi| = n \\ k+1 \leq s(\pi)}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} (1 + z + \dots + z^{s(\pi)-1}) \quad \text{and then}$$

establish the Corollary 2: $FFW(1, n) = FFW(n)$.

2. SOME RELATED DEFINITIONS

$P(n)$ [Sabuj et al (2014b)]: The number of partitions of n like

$$4, 3+1, 2+2, 2+1+1, 1+1+1+1 \quad \therefore P(4) = 5.$$

FFW (n) [Fokkink et al (1995)]: Let D denote the set of partitions into distinct parts. We define;

$$FFW (n) = \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi|=n}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} s(\pi),$$

where $s(\pi)$ is the smallest part of π , and $\#(\pi)$ is the number of parts .

$d(n)$: The numbers of positive divisors of n like $d(1)=1, d(2)=2, d(3)=2,..$

Product Notations [Sabuj et al (2014a)]:

$$(x; x)_{\infty} = (x)_{\infty} = (1 - x)(1 - x^2)(1 - x^3)...$$

$$(x^2; x)_{\infty} = (1 - x^2)(1 - x^3)...$$

$$(zx)_{\infty} = (1 - zx)(1 - zx^2)....$$

$$(x)_k = (1 - x)(1 - x^2) ... (1 - x^k)$$

$$(x^{k+1}; x)_{\infty} = (1 - x^{k+1})(1 - x^{k+2}).....$$

3. WE GIVE TWO TABLES FOR n= 5 AND 6 RESPECTIVELY

Table-1: Partition of 5 into distinct parts.

Partition of 5 into distinct parts	Smallest part of (π) $s(\pi)$
5	5
4+1	1
3+2	2

From the table we get;

$$FFW (5) = (-1)^0 5 + (-1)^1 .1 + (-1)^1 .2 = 5-1 -2 =2.$$

Table-2: Partition of 6 into distinct parts.

Partition of 6 into distinct parts	Smallest part of (π) $s(\pi)$
6	6
5+1	1
4+2	2
3+2+1	1

From the table we get;

$$FFW (6) = 6-1-2+1 =7-3=4.$$

Similarly we get;

$$FFW (1) =1, FFW (2) =2, FFW (3) = 2, FFW (4) =3.....$$

The generating Function [Andrews (2008)] for FFW (n) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n+1}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-x^n)} \\ &= \frac{x}{(1-x)(1-x)} + \frac{(-1) \cdot x^3}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^3)} + \dots \\ &= x + 2x^2 + 2x^3 + 3x^4 + 2x^5 + 4x^6 + \dots \\ &= FFW (1) x + FFW (2)x^2 + FFW (3)x^3 + FFW(4)x^4 + \dots \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(n)x^n . \end{aligned}$$

A relation related to the term d (n).

We get; $FFW (1) = 1 = d (1)$

$FFW (2) = 2= d (2)$

$FFW (3) = 2= d (3)$

$FFW (4) = 3= d (4)$

$FFW (5) = 2= d (5)$

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We can write the relation $FFW(n) = d (n)$.

4. NOW WE DESCRIBE THE VARIOUS GENERATING FUNCTIONS [Andrews et al 2001] FOR FFW (z, n)

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1-zx^n)(x)_n} \\ &= \frac{x}{(1-x)(1-zx)} - \frac{x^3}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-zx^2)} + \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-zx^3)} - \dots \\ &= x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + \\ & \quad (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4+z^5+1)x^6 + \dots \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW (z, n)x^n \end{aligned}$$

We get; $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(x)_k} [(x)_k - (x)_{\infty}]$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \{1 - (x)_{\infty}\} + \frac{z}{(1-x)} \{(1-x) - (x)_{\infty}\} + \frac{z^2}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} \{(1-x)(1-x^2) - (x)_{\infty}\} + \frac{z^3}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} \\ & \quad \{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3) - (x)_{\infty}\} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &= x + x^2 + z(x^2 + x^3 + x^4) + z^2(x^3 + x^4) + z^3x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + \dots \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n .
 \end{aligned}$$

Again we get; $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} z^k \{1 - (x^{k+1}; x)_{\infty}\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \{1 - (x)_{\infty}\} + z\{1 - (x^2; x)_{\infty}\} + z^2\{1 - (x^3; x)_{\infty}\} + \dots \\
 &= \{1 + z + z^2 + z^3 + \dots\} - \{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots + z(1-x)(1-x^3)\dots + z^2(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots\} \\
 &= \{1 + z + z^2 + z^3 + \dots\} - \{1 - x - x^2 + z - zx^2 - zx^3 + z^2 - z^2x^3 + \dots\} \\
 &= x + x^2 + z(x^2 + x^3 + x^4) + z^2(x^3 + x^4) + z^3x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + \dots \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n .
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary1: $\frac{x}{(1-zx)(1-x)} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{z^k-1}{z-1}\right) x^k.$

Proof: L.H.S = $\frac{x}{(1-zx)(1-x)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= x(1+zx+z^2x^2+z^3x^3+\dots)(1+x+x^2+x^3+\dots) \\
 &= x + (1+z)x^2 + (1+z+z^2)x^3 + (1+z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + \frac{(1+z)(1-z)}{(1-z)}x^2 + \frac{(1+z+z^2)(1-z)}{(1-z)}x^3 + \frac{(1+z+z^2+z^3)(1-z)}{(1-z)}x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + \frac{(1-z^2)}{(1-z)}x^2 + \frac{(1-z^3)}{(1-z)}x^3 + \frac{(1-z^4)}{(1-z)}x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + \frac{(z^2-1)}{(z-1)}x^2 + \frac{(z^3-1)}{(z-1)}x^3 + \frac{(z^4-1)}{(z-1)}x^4 + \dots \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{z^k-1}{z-1}\right) x^k = R.H.S. . \quad \text{Hence The Corollary.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1: $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1-zx^n)(x)_n} = \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{1 - \frac{(x)_{\infty}}{(zx)_{\infty}}\right\}.$

Proof: we get; $\frac{x^5}{1-x} = x^5(1+x+x^2+x^3+\dots)$

Or, $x^1x^4 \frac{1}{(x)_1} = x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$

is the generating function for partitions into 2 distinct parts with smallest part 2 like the required partitions 3+2, 4+2,respectively.

$$\text{Again } \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} = x^6(1+x+x^2+x^3+\dots)(1+x^2+x^4+\dots) \\ = x^6(1+x+x^2+x^4+\dots)$$

Or, $x^3 \cdot x^3 \frac{1}{(x)_2} = x^6 + x^7 + 2x^8 + \dots$ is the generating function for partitions into 3 distinct parts with smallest part 1 like the required partitions are 3+2+1, 4+2+1,respectively. Now we see that

$x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \frac{1}{(x)_{n-1}}$ is the generation function for partitions into n distinct parts with smallest part k.

$$\text{Thus } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^n + (1+z)x^{2n} + \dots + (1+z+\dots+z^{k-1})x^{kn} + \dots) \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ x^n + \frac{(1+z)(1-z)}{(1-z)} x^{2n} + \frac{(1+z+z^2)(1-z)}{(1-z)} x^{3n} + \dots \right\} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ x^n + \frac{z^2-1}{z-1} x^{2n} + \frac{z^3-1}{z-1} x^{3n} + \dots \right\} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^k-1}{z-1} x^{kn} \right) \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(1-zx^n)(1-x^n)} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} \quad [\text{by Corollary 1}]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1-zx^n)(x)_n}$$

[Since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1-x^n)(x)_{n-1} = (1-x) + (1-x^2)(1-x) + (1-x^3)(1-x^2)(1-x) + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x)_n$]

$$\text{Or, 1st part} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1-zx^n)(x)_n} = 2^{\text{nd}} \text{ part}$$

$$\text{Now } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1-zx^n)(x)_n} = \frac{x}{(1-zx)(1-x)} - \frac{x^3}{(1-zx^2)(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \dots$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ \frac{x(1-z)}{(1-zx)(1-x)} - \frac{x^3(1-z)}{(1-zx^2)(1-x)(1-zx^2)} + \dots \right\} = \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - 1 + \frac{x(1-z)}{(1-zx)(1-x)} - \dots \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \frac{x(1-z)}{(1-zx)(1-x)} + \dots \right\} \right] = \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}} (z)_n}{(x)_n (zx)_n} \dots \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-z)} \{ 1 - (1 - (1-z)x - (1-z^2)x^2 + \dots) \} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-z)} \{ 1 - (1-x-x^2+x^5+\dots)(1+zx+(z+z^2)x^2+\dots) \} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - \frac{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots}{(1-zx)(1-zx^2)(1-zx^3)\dots} \right\} = \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - \frac{(x)_\infty}{(zx)_\infty} \right\} = 3^{\text{rd}} \text{ Part.}
 \end{aligned}$$

But $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}} (z)_n}{(x)_n (zx)_n} = \frac{(x)_\infty}{(zx)_\infty}$ [Andrews (1976)]

$\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1-zx^n)(x)_n} = \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - \frac{(x)_\infty}{(zx)_\infty} \right\}$. Hence The Theorem.

Theorem 2: $FFW(z, n) = \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi|=n \\ k+1 \leq s(\pi)}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} (1+z+\dots+z^{s(\pi)-1})$.

Proof: We get; $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(x)_k} [(x)_k - (x)_\infty]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \{1 - (x)_\infty\} + \frac{z}{(1-x)} \{ (1-x) - (x)_\infty \} + \frac{z^2}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} \{ (1-x)(1-x^2) - (x)_\infty \} + \frac{z^3}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} \\
 &\{ (1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3) - (x)_\infty \} + \dots \\
 &= \{1 - (x)_\infty\} + z\{1 - (1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots\} + z^2\{1 - (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots\} \\
 &= \{1 - (x)_\infty\} + z\{1 - (x^2; x)_\infty\} + z^2\{1 - (x^3; x)_\infty\} + \dots = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} z^k \{1 - (x^{k+1}; x)_\infty\} \\
 \therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} z^k \{1 - (x^{k+1}; x)_\infty\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We see that the co-efficient of $z^k x^n$ in right hand side

$$\text{is } \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi|=n \\ k+1 \leq s(\pi)}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} (1+z+\dots+z^{s(\pi)-1})$$

which is also co-efficient of $z^k x^n$ in left hand side.

$$\therefore \text{FFW}(z, n) = \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi|=n \\ k+1 \leq s(\pi)}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} (1+z+\dots+z^{s(\pi)-1}). \text{Hence the Theorem.}$$

Corollary 2: $\text{FFW}(1, n) = \text{FFW}(n)$

Proof: We get;
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-zx^n)}$$

$$= x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + (-1+1+z^2+z^3+z^4+z^5)x^6 + \dots$$

Or,
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{FFW}(z, n)x^n = x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + \dots$$

If $z=1$, we get;

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{FFW}(1, n)x^n = x + 2x^2 + 2x^3 + 3x^4 + 2x^5 + 4x^6 + \dots$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-x^n)} \quad (\text{by above})$$

$$\text{Or, } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{FFW}(1, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{FFW}(n)x^n .$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n form both sides we get;

$$\therefore \text{FFW}(1, n) = \text{FFW}(n). \text{Hence the Corollary.}$$

5. CONCLUSION

In this study we have found the number of partitions of n into distinct parts with required conditions. We have already shown the numbers of partitions for $n = 5$ and 6 respectively and have found the number of partitions from the relation $\text{FFW}(n) = d(n)$ for any positive integral of n . We have proved the Theorem 1 containing two generating functions

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-zx^n)} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - \frac{(x)_{\infty}}{(zx)_{\infty}} \right\}$$

with the help of generating functions for partitions into n distinct parts with smallest part k and have proved the Theorem 2 by taking the co-efficient from various two generating functions. Finally we have established the Corollary $FFW(1, n) = FFW(n)$ by taking $z=1$.

6. REFERENCES

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